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Designing a network of Green Infrastructure for the EU

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Abstract

The EU's Green Infrastructure Strategy aims at developing a strategically planned network of natural and semi-natural areas to support the maintenance of ecosystem services (ESS) and connect protected areas (PAs), promoting in this way multifunctional landscapes. This network of GI aims to address the decline in ESS across the EU and also contribute to achieving the objectives of the Biodiversity Strategy, such as halting biodiversity loss.

Here, we demonstrate how a spatial planning tool could be used for designing a network of GI across the EU. We tested two alternative planning scenarios: an EU-based, where the full network is planned at the continental scale, and a country-based scenario, where independent planning exercises are made by each EU member State. Both scenarios pursued the same objectives: to cover the distribution of 767 vertebrate species and 229 habitats under a "conservation management zone" and to warrant the provision of 5 ESS under the GI network, while connecting existing PAs already designated as Natura 2000.

A systematically planned GI could warrant ESS provision and increase the connectivity of N2000 sites, while improving the coverage of species of EU-conservation interest beyond current protected areas. This network of GI is allocated in similar proportions on forested and agricultural areas. The EU-based planned GI was more efficient (less area needed for achieving targets) than the Country-based one for intermediate-large targets, including more areas along borders between countries, rather than consolidating connectivity among PAs within each country. Country-based solutions collectively achieved the EU targets. However, while all targets for species, habitats and ESS could be achieved under the EU-based scenario, targets for some ESS (especially Carbon

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retention) could not be fully achieved under the country-based scenario for some countries.

Our results demonstrate the benefits of cross-country collaboration when designing the future network of GI in the EU and highlights the need for more robust policy instruments to support the designation and management of this network to secure integration in other sectorial policies and funding.

Keywords: Biodiversity Strategy, habitats, ecosystem services, climate change, Marxan with Zones, optimization.

Introduction

There is increasing global concern about the fast degradation of ecosystem services (ESS) and the rapid decline of biodiversity (MEA, 2005; WWF, 2018). The recent assessment on biodiversity and ESS by the Intergovernmental Panel on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) warns that nature across most of the globe has been significantly altered by multiple human drivers, with the great majority of indicators for ecosystems and biodiversity showing rapid decline (IPBES, 2019). The deterioration of natural ecosystems threatens the persistence of more than 25% of all species, many in risk of extinction within decades, and the future maintenance of ESS they support (Duffy et al., 2017). All these changes also compromise future human wellbeing. In the EU, Maes et al. (2015a) reported declines in ESS of 5.2% delivery compared to 2010. Under these scenarios, there is an urgent need for conservation efforts to halt the degradation of ecosystems and foster the sustainable use of multi-functional landscapes. This requires adequate planning to help harmonizing biodiversity conservation and maintenance of ESS with other legitimate societal objectives competing for limited space and resources (UN General Assembly, 2015).

In response to the rapid decline of natural ecosystems, the EU has developed policies focused on securing sustainable provision of ESS, the protection of natural capital and the development of strategies to cope with potentially changing conditions in the future (e.g. climate change; Maes et al., 2015a). However, management of natural ecosystems cannot be restricted to areas within PAs' borders. Integrated planning for biodiversity and ESS beyond PA boundaries seems unavoidable because species' are expected to shift their distribution ranges under climate change, potentially reducing the effectiveness of current conservation efforts within PAs (Araújo et al., 2011). In this

line, the EU in 2013 laid the foundations to create a network of Green Infrastructure (GI) (European Commission, 2013a). This network of GI is viewed as a “strategically planned network of natural and semi-natural areas designed and managed to deliver a wide range of ESS and stop the loss of biodiversity” (European Commission, 2013a). Two key objectives guide the designation of this network: i) to enhance connectivity between PAs to allow species to thrive across their entire natural habitat, and adapt to effects of climate change, and ii) to contribute to the maintenance of ESS delivery to society. The Natura 2000, the network of PAs in the EU, is the backbone of this network of Green Infrastructure. New areas must now be strategically added to connect PAs and foster landscape multifunctionality (European Commission, 2013a). Recognizing that the matrix in between protected areas also have conservation value and managing it accordingly is key to achieve the aims of the EU Biodiversity Strategy, of halting biodiversity loss (European Commission, 2011; Hermoso et al., 2019).

Given potential conflicts between different interests on a highly populated landscape where there is high competition for land between different uses (e.g. urban, agriculture, conservation), strategic decisions are unavoidable (Verhagen et al., 2018). The integration of these multiple objectives can be explicitly addressed through spatial planning tools to minimise potential their conflicts and enhance co-benefits (Howe et al., 2014). In the EU, large scale planning exercises have been carried out to identify priority areas for biodiversity conservation (e.g., Kukkala et al., 2018; Kark et al., 2009) or securing access to ESS (e.g., Vallecillo et al., 2018; Maes et al., 2012). However, the integration of these two objectives simultaneously in a single planning exercise has only been carried out at smaller scales (e.g., Domisch et al., 2019; Lanzas et al., 2019; Barbosa et al., 2019). Therefore, there is still a knowledge gap on how to design this

strategic network of GI that pursues ESS and biodiversity conservation objectives at the EU level.

Here, we demonstrate how a spatial planning tool - based on the identification of clear conservation and ESS objectives- can be used to design a comprehensive, multi-objective network of GI across the EU to enhance connectivity among PAs and warrant the provision of ESS. We assess the implications of the setting GI priorities at different policy scales (national vs continental). For this, we tested two alternative scenarios for planning this network of GI: an EU-based scenario, where the full GI network is planned at the continental level, and a country-based scenario, where separate GI planning exercises are carried out for each EU member state. We evaluate the pros and cons of each scenario and provide guidance on how systematic planning could be used to design a future network of GI in the EU. With this exercise we intend to provide tools to future integrated planning for multifunctional landscapes, which has been long demanded in EU's policy (European Environment Agency, 2014). We used the best available data on distribution of vertebrates, habitats and ESS at the continental scale and integrated them in a prioritisation exercise to identify new management areas outside the current N2000 network that could help achieve the two-tiered objective of the EU GI network.

Methods

Ecosystem services, species and habitats data

We used maps developed by Maes et al. (2015b) on five ESS of major relevance across EU: carbon retention, capacity to avoid soil erosion, water retention, pollination

potential and recreational opportunity. These maps represent potential values for service provision rather than ES demand (Maes et al., 2015a, but see Vallecillo et al., 2018).

This information was available in raster format at 100 m resolution. We translated each ecosystem service at the 10x10 km grid resolution by summing up the value of services within each grid cell. In this way, we obtained a measure of the total potential of each service for each 10 km grid cell across EU. We used this spatial resolution as reference for our spatial planning analysis (planning units).

The spatial distribution of 767 vertebrate species was sourced from the IUCN Red List (IUCN, 2018) and BirdLife International NatureServe (2015) and translated into the 10 x10 km grids. These distribution maps convey the extent of occurrence of species (Syfert et al. 2014) and represent the best standardised source of distribution data for all vertebrates in the EU, commonly used for large-scale assessments like this in Europe (Carrizo et al., 2017; Kark et al., 2009) and elsewhere (Allan et al., 2019; Girardello et al., 2019; Venter et al., 2014). To be conservative, only the areas where the species are native to (origin=native) with a high certainty (presence= extant) were retained for the analyses.

We also compiled maps of the spatial distribution of 229 habitats, sourced from the European Red List of Habitats assessment (Janssen et al., 2016). These maps represent the most comprehensive distribution of habitats across the whole of the EU at 10x10 km resolution for the level 3 of the EUNIS habitat classification divisions (EUNIS, 2007).

Prioritisation of a network of green infrastructure

To prioritise the allocation of a network of GI (i.e. where new areas of management outside the N2000 network should be located), we used the software Marxan with Zones (Watts et al., 2009). Marxan with Zones uses a simulated annealing optimisation algorithm to try to minimise an objective function similar to Marxan (Ball et al., 2009). The objective function in Marxan is composed of three different parameters: i) the cost associated to the management of all planning units in the solution, ii) penalties for not achieving targets for all conservation features (species, habitats and ESS here), and iii) connectivity penalties for not achieving spatially clustered solutions. The overall aim of this exercise was to minimise the cost of representing all conservation features in a connected network of priority management areas. The objective function used in Marxan with Zones is slightly more complex as there is more than one management zone (i.e. what standard Marxan does). In Marxan with Zones there are penalties for unachieved representation targets for conservation features or missing connectivity both within and across zones (see Watts et al., 2009 for further details on the mathematical formulation of Marxan with Zones). In our planning exercise, we considered two different management zones: (1) a conservation zone, that resembles the role of the Natura 2000 network focused on the protection of species and habitats, and (2) a green infrastructure zone, that seeks to fulfil the double objective pursued by this GI as described in EU policy: to increase connectivity between conservation zones, and secure maintenance of ESS at the same time.

Marxan with Zones

We translated the different objectives detailed above into Marxan with Zones' parametrisation by using different input files and parameters (Table1). Marxan with Zones uses the basic input files of Marxan: (1) a *Planning units* file listing all planning

units considered in the analyses and specifying how costly each planning unit would be (*cost* parameter; Table 1); (2) a *Species file* listing all conservation features in the analyses – here species, ESS and habitats – and the amount of each of them that we want to cover or represent in the optimal solution (*targets* parameter; Table1); (3) a *planning units vs species* file, that allocates the distribution of conservation features across space (Puvspr file; Table 1) and, (4) a *Boundary* file (Table1) that informs Marxan about how the planning units are connected in space (Table1). The only difference in Marxan with Zones' basic input files is that the *Planning units* file allows for inclusion of multiple costs (different for each zone) compared to the unique cost assumed in Marxan. We used the average human footprint (Venter et al., 2016) within each 10-km grid cell as a penalty for its selection in Marxan solutions. The human footprint is a cumulative index that summarises different pressures derived from human activities, such as infrastructure or agriculture and it is standardised for the whole study area, as required for the analyses. We used the human footprint as a subrogate of 'cost' (sensu Naidoo et al., 2007), assuming that the higher the human footprint, the less suitable a planning unit would be for conservation purposes or the more expensive it would be its management for conservation of biodiversity or maintenance of ESS (i.e. more restoration needed). Given that both management zones included in this exercise seek similar conservation/management goals (either biodiversity or ESS) we decided to apply the same cost to both of them. So, each planning unit had a single cost associated depending on their average human footprint; we assumed that the more impacted by human uses planning units were, the less suitable for being part of either management zones.

We set a minimum representation target for species and habitats of 1,000 km², whenever possible. This target represents the whole distribution range for the 70 rarest species across EU, >25% of the distribution extent of 147 species, the full distribution of the two rarest habitats and >25% of the distribution range of 16 habitats. The proportional representation of the remaining species and habitats (all with distribution extents >40,000 km²) declined proportionally with their extent of occurrence, to avoid overrepresenting very common species and habitats in the solutions. For example, a similar target of 25% of a species distributed across 40,000 planning units (59 species in our database), would have meant demanding the selection of almost ¼ of the whole EU. On the other hand, given the central role of ESS in the designation of the EU network of GI, we ran multiple analyses to explore the impact of setting different ESS target values on the spatial configuration and total extent of the network of GI (sensitivity analysis). We evaluated four increasing targets for all ESS: 5, 10, 25 and 50% of their total value across the EU, while maintained constant representation targets for biodiversity. We repeated this sensitivity analysis for the two alternative planning scenarios tested here (see next section).

We split representation targets across the two management zones described above. Targets for species and habitats were allocated in the conservation zone, while targets for ESS were allocated in the GI zone. In this way, planning units selected to be part of the conservation management zone would mainly contribute to representing the distribution of species and habitats, while planning units under the GI zone would help achieve targets for ESS. This does not mean that planning units under the conservation zone do not have value for ESS, but that these values do not contribute to the achievement of representation targets of ESS that still need to be represented under the

GI zone. We specified this in the *Zone contribution* file in Marxan with Zones (Table 1).

Connectivity played a key role in the design of the network of GI, given its value as connector among conservation zones. We used two different features of Marxan with Zones to achieve i) internal connectivity within zones and ii) connectivity between zones. This later feature would help us design a network of GI that serves as connectivity matrix among conservation zones. To address connectivity, we used the *Boundary* file (Table 1). This file contains all pairwise adjacency relationships for each planning unit and the length of the boundary shared with these neighbours. This file is normally used to achieve clumped solutions of planning units and therefore maximize internal connectivity (e.g., Hermoso et al., 2018). To specify the spatial relationship between the two management zones and achieve a network of GI that connects conservation zones we used the *Zone boundary* file in Marxan with Zones (Table 1). We followed recommendations in Watts et al. (2008) to calibrate this file and achieve the desired spatial relationship between zones: green infrastructure connecting conservation zones.

We finally accounted for the distribution of the Natura 2000 network in the planning exercise. To translate the distribution of the Natura 2000 network into our planning units, we measured the proportion of each planning unit covered by Natura 2000 sites. A planning unit was considered to be protected when more than 25% of its extent was covered by the Natura 2000 network. We could not mark as protected all planning units that contained at least one Natura 2000 sites as some of these sites are very small (19% of PAs in Natura 2000 have $< 0.25 \text{ km}^2$) covering only a small portion of 10 x10 km planning units. For this reason, the set of planning units identified here are not a faithful

representation of the Natura 2000 network, but a selection of those planning units more representative of this network, for planning purposes at the continental scale. A total of 12,033 planning units fulfilled this threshold and were locked in solutions in Marxan with Zones under the conservation zone (through the *Pulock* file; Table 1). This forced the selection of all these planning units under the conservation zone. Whenever representation targets could not be achieved within these locked in planning units, Marxan with Zones tried to identify a minimum set of additional planning units to complement them, to achieve the representation targets for species and habitats set for this zone.

With this configuration, we ran Marxan with Zones 100 times, 10 Million iterations each and retained the solution with the lowest objective function across all runs for subsequent analyses (*best solution* hereafter). To compare solutions obtained from this multi-zoning approach against an analysis in which we sought to achieve same ESS and biodiversity targets using single-zone planning approach (standard Marxan; Ball et al., 2009). We used the same targets and SPF for each feature, locked in Natura 2000 and set the BLM to the same value used in Marxan with Zones. With this configuration we ran standard Marxan 100 times (10 Million iterations each) under the two alternative planning scenarios described below.

Planning scenarios

We tested two alternative planning scenarios: i) EU-based planning, that aims coordinated planning across the EU, where all countries contribute as a single entity to the representation targets for species, habitats and ESS; and ii) a Country-based planning, in which each country contributes proportionally to the representation of each species, habitat or ESS according to their total contribution of the EU distribution. So,

we translated targets set at the EU level into country targets. For example, if two countries held 50% of the distribution of a given species each, under the EU-based scenario, there were no restrictions to the total share that each of these countries could make to target achievement, so a single country could contribute to the full achievement of targets and no other contribution from the other country would be needed. Under the Country-based scenario, both countries had to contribute at least with 50% of the target demanded for that species. These two scenarios represent two extremes in which the design of the GI is planned at the EU-level scale or at the country-scale (i.e. without considering the presence of protected areas, or conservation features of relevance beyond the boundaries of each country). In summary, we run Marxan with Zones and standard Marxan for two scenarios (EU- vs Country-based) assuming four different ESS targets 5, 10, 25, and 50 in each scenario for a total of 8 planning solutions (EU5 to EU50, for the EU-based planning scenario and Country5 to Country50 for Country-based planning scenario respectively).

Comparison between scenarios

We checked the representation of species, habitats and ESS under each of the two management zones of the *best solution* of each planning scenario. We measured the proportion of the total distribution of species and habitats distribution in the EU covered under each management zone and the proportion of the total amount of each ecosystem service represented under these management zones.

To evaluate improvements in connectivity in our solutions compared to the current connectivity of the Natura 2000 network (as used in this study) we used the *Boundary* file in Marxan. We calculated a connectivity index (CInx) as the ratio between the connections achieved vs. total potential connections for the set of planning units in the

best solution. All planning units assigned to the conservation zone and the GI zone were considered in this calculation. $CInx$ ranges between 0, when none of the potential connections among planning units in the *best solution* were achieved, and 1, when all potential connections between planning units in the *best solution* were included. This index is suitable for comparing *best solutions* regardless difference in the number of planning units included in each of them, given that the connectivity achieved is always referred to the maximum potential for a given set of planning units. We calculated the $CInx$ for the set of planning units currently covered by the Natura 2000 network, and for the *best solutions* across both scenarios and sensitivity analyses [$Difference=(CInx_{BestSolution}-CInx_{Natura2000})/CInx_{BestSolution}$]. We also compared the CI index values within countries under both scenarios [$Difference=(CInx_{EU}-CInx_{country})/CInx_{EU}$]. Finally, we compared $CInx$ for solutions obtained in standard Marxan and Marxan with Zones.

We also characterised the degradation status of planning units selected under each management zone, by checking the frequency distribution of human footprint values (Venter et al., 2016) across all planning units selected under each management zone. We further tested for significant differences in human footprint values across management zones via one-way ANOVA for each planning scenario. We would expect planning units under the conservation and green infrastructure zones to be on average less impacted by human activities, than planning units not selected for these management zones. To further characterise the status of management zones, we checked the dominant land cover of planning units under each management zone. We grouped the different classes in the Corine Land Cover 2012 (EEA, 2016) into four types: urban/ industrial, agriculture, natural and wetlands (Appendix A) and selected the dominant

land cover of each 10- km grid cell. We then measured the proportion of each management zone covered by these land use types across different scenarios.

Results

The targets set for species and habitats were achieved for all *best solutions* across both scenarios in the conservation zone. All targets for ESS were also achieved in the GI zone under the EU-based planning scenario, and only not achieved in some cases under the country-based scenario, for the highest target level (50% of ESS; Appendix B), and despite the increase in the amount of some ESS covered (Fig. 1). This higher representation of ESS under the Country-based scenario was due to overachievement of targets for some ESS in particular countries (e.g., C retention in Finland), and mainly due to incidental representation of these ESS in planning units selected for other features in areas where these ESS are abundant. Carbon retention was the most commonly reported ESS that could not achieve targets under the country-based scenario (Appendix B).

The conservation zone covered on average 40% and 46% of the distribution of all species and habitats respectively and 1/3 of all ESS in the EU across all scenarios tested (Fig. 1). On the other hand, coverage of ESS in the GI zone showed differences across planning scenarios for intermediate-large targets (EU25 and EU50). The GI zone covered on average 29% of ESS in the EU5, EU10 and EU25 scenarios and 51% for the EU50 scenario, and 29% of ESS in the Country5 and Country10 scenarios, and 33% and 55% of ESS under the Country25 and Country50 scenarios respectively (Fig. 1). On the other hand, although there were no targets on species and habitats explicitly set

under the GI zone, this zone also covered biodiversity conservation features by incidental representation of areas selected for ESS (Fig. 1). This coverage was similar under low targets across planning scenarios (29% for species and 27% for habitats) and different for intermediate-high targets (44% and 40% for species and habitats under the EU50 vs. 50% and 43% for the Country50).

We did not find large differences in the extent and spatial allocation of management zones across scenarios for low targets (5 and 10%) and increasing differences in the extent of the GI zone under intermediate-high targets (25% and 50%; Table 2, Appendix C). The conservation zone was mostly formed by the Natura 2000 network (26% of all planning units), and only a few additional planning units were added on top of the already locked ones (Appendix D). The GI zone did show differences across intermediate-high targets in both scenarios. It was constant for targets EU5, EU10 and EU25 (28% planning units), while increased up to 50% of planning units for the EU50 target under the EU-based scenario. In the case of the Country-based scenario the GI zone increased from 26% to 55% under the Country5 and Country50 scenarios respectively (Table2). The differences in the extent of planning units selected at the country level across both planning scenarios were more obvious in the GI zone (Table 2; Appendix D, E). For intermediate targets of 25%, in some countries the extent of the GI zone included 30% more planning units under the country-based scenario than the EU-based scenario (Appendix D), while in others, the extent of the GI zone decreased when planning under the country-based scenario (Appendix D). The differences in the extent of the GI zone between both planning scenarios was more obvious for the 50% target, with increases in extent for most of countries, some >40% of additional planning units (Appendix E).

There was an overall improvement in connectivity between Natura 2000 sites when adding the GI zone, although there was country-specific variability in this result (Appendix F). When adding the GI zone, the CInx experienced increases around 50%, compared to the connectivity of Natura 2000 alone. This was constant along the different targets on ESS tested (Appendix F). When comparing CInx between both planning scenarios, we found that there were within country differences (Appendix G). There were also increasing differences in the proportion of unique planning units in the GI zone under the EU-based vs. country-based scenarios. This proportion increased from 7% to 27% from the EU5 to EU50 (9% and 15% for the EU10 and EU25 targets respectively). These unique planning units to any of the scenarios were allocated differently in space. While planning units unique to the EU-based scenario were mainly allocated along borders between countries, planning units unique to the country-based scenario were allocated between PAs within countries (Fig. 1 C-E).

The areas under the conservation zone showed the lowest values of Human Footprint constantly across analyses, followed by the GI zone and no-management zones (Fig. 3). These differences were especially significant in the case of the EU50 scenario, being the areas on poorest condition left under no-management. The difference in Human Footprint across zones was more attenuated under the country-based scenario, reflecting that the GI zone needed the selection of areas in poorer condition to achieve targets when planned at the country scale than when planned jointly across the EU (Fig. 3). These results were also confirmed by the coverage of land uses within each management zone. The conservation zone mostly covered areas under natural vegetation and wetlands regardless the planning scenario (Fig. 4). The GI zone was covered almost equally by Natural vegetation and agricultural areas regardless the

planning scenario. The largest land cover types contributors to the GI zone were “Non-irrigated arable land” (32% and 31% of all GI zone under the EU-based and country-based scenarios respectively), “Coniferous forest” (18% and 20%) and “Broad-leaved forest”, (12% and 11%), although with differences across countries (Appendix A, H). Other important land cover types contributing to <10% were “Pastures” (7% of GI in both scenarios) and “Mixed forest” (4% and 5% under the EU-based and country-based scenarios respectively; Appendix A).

Finally, the no-management zone showed the largest coverage by urban and agricultural land of all zones, especially significant under the 50% target for EU-based planning scenario (Fig. 4).

Solutions obtained from standard Marxan (i.e. the single-zone planning approach), showed that there was no need to add planning units to those already locked in as Natura 2000, for targets <25% on ESS (for both EU- and country-based planning scenarios). The number of planning units added to achieve targets for the remaining target scenarios was always higher when planning under the Country-based scenario than when planning under the EU-based scenario (Appendix H). Moreover, the connectivity achieved under the single-zone planning approach was not different from the already existing under the Natura 2000 (Appendix I), and therefore, only half the connectivity achieved in solutions with Marxan with Zones.

Discussion

Here, we have demonstrated how a network of GI could be strategically planned across the EU to fulfil a two-tiered objective: enhance connectivity among PAs, mostly already

designated under Natura 2000, through areas with a high potential for maintaining ESS at the same time. The European Parliament on its “Action Plan for nature, people and the economy” (European Parliament, 2017) calls for a genuine proposal for the development of a Trans-European Network for Green Infrastructure (TEN-G) and a better use of integrated spatial planning processes. In its recent global report, the IPBES also claims for the need of “planning ecologically representative networks of interconnected protected areas to cover key biodiversity areas and managing trade-offs between societal objectives that represent diverse worldviews and multiple values of nature” (REF). With this exercise, we aimed at providing tools to fulfil this long-demanded need for integrated spatial planning at the continental scale and fill some gaps of previous studies on GI and spatial planning at national to continental scales. We show that by using the current network of PAs as a backbone, a network of GI could be designed across the EU covering areas with a large potential for ESS provision, allocated in similar proportions on forested and agricultural areas. The management of this network of GI will need financial support under existing tools in EU’s policy. Given the importance of agricultural and forestry areas, sectorial policies such as the Common Agricultural Policy will play a key role in the management of the network of GI.

The future European network of GI must be an opportunity to manage multifunctional landscapes for maintaining ESS, long claimed by international conventions (SDG, IPBES), but also biodiversity under changing conditions (Hermoso et al., 2019). The network of GI planned in this study aims to be multifunctional as areas are jointly selected for multiple objectives. On one hand, the areas identified here have a high potential to provide multiple ESS at the same time (Maes et al., 2015a). The principle of

complementarity that guides the selection of areas in Marxan with Zones, gives higher priority to areas that provide the highest values for multiple ESS at the same time (Margules and Pressey, 2000). Moreover, the areas selected here were optimised for connecting Natura 2000 sites, bringing additional functionality to the network of GI. By connecting PAs, we enhance the capacity of Natura 2000 to cope with the EU's biodiversity conservation challenge imposed by climate and land use change and their associated dynamism (IPBES, 2019). Species ranges are expected to shift in the future (Araújo et al., 2011) and conservation efforts outside the limits of PAs seems unavoidable. Designating more PAs (or readjusting them as change happens) is too difficult in a highly-humanised continent with competing objectives for limited territory and funds (Hermoso et al., 2019). The network of GI not only helps connect Natura 2000 sites, but also increases coverage of the distribution ranges of EU's vertebrates demonstrating the high potential to manage biodiversity outside PAs along with ESS.

As we demonstrate the planning scenario (EU vs. country-based) had limited influence of the spatial extent and allocation of the network of GI. The EU-based scenario showed to be more efficient at achieving the targets, at intermediate-large targets (25-50%), but less efficient for the low targets (5-10%). This pattern was probably due to the spatial constraints imposed in the prioritisation process, since we locked in the full extent of the Natura 2000 (26% of all planning units) across all solutions and sought a high connectivity among them to fulfil one of the key objectives of this network of GI: serve as a connector among PAs. This latter constraint was stronger in the EU-based planning scenario as more connections were considered, both within the country boundaries and also across countries. When planning for low targets (5 and 10%), the Country-based outperformed the EU-based planning approach as less units were needed to fulfil

targets. As targets increased, the impact of connectivity on planning efficiency made the EU-based scenario outperform the Country-based one. The country-based planning failed to achieve targets especially for Carbon retention within the network of GI. This might be because most of the value of these ESS were either already covered within PAs or because Marxan with zones found it hard to represent ESS within the GI zone due to the high “cost” (Human Footprint in this case) of the areas where they appear. However, the collective contribution of each country to the overall representation of ESS resembled or surpassed the EU-based results, and would be enough as to achieve the EU-based targets. The large representation of ESS under the Country-based scenario was mainly due to overachievement of some targets at National level due to incidental representation. This highlights potential duplicities at EU-level of Country-based planning approaches (Kark et al., 2009). Moreover, the EU-based scenario led to a better TEN-G. When planning at the EU scale, some critical GI areas appeared along the borders of countries to ensure a more comprehensive connection of Natura 2000 sites across borders and then not only connecting PAs within each State, but also across the whole EU. On the other hand, when planning at the country scale, some of these connections between countries were not achieved while within country connectivity received more attention, with more GI planning units allocated for connecting National PAs. Similar improvement of connectivity across countries has been shown when planning at continental (Kark et al., 2009) or other supra-National levels (e.g., whole river catchments, Allan et al., 2019) when identifying priority areas for biodiversity conservation. As we show with the single-zone planning exercise, the GI zone is crucial for addressing this connectivity. When using only a management zone that resembles PAs (standard Marxan), the improvement in connectivity was far from the scenarios

where we used multiple zones including the GI. Finally, the Country-based scenario needed the inclusion of more agricultural areas and coniferous and mixed forest to achieve the targets than the EU-based scenario, making Country-based planning less cost-efficient than EU-based planning. The additional forest areas were mainly allocated in a couple of countries (Finland and Sweden, Appendix H) due to uneven distribution of ESS associated to forest across the EU (e.g. Piovesan and Adams, 2000), while the agricultural areas were more evenly contributed by a larger group of countries. These results show the benefits of EU-integrated planning when aiming at large targets on ESS, to ensure fully achievement of targets in a cost-effective way. Finally, the GI derived from the EU-based planning scenario was more effective at avoiding highly degraded areas (measured as the magnitude of the Human Footprint), especially at large targets. This is relevant as the areas in poor condition (e.g., degraded ecosystems), are less suitable for providing ESS (Maes et al., 2015a; Valecillo et al., 2018) and also hinder the long-term provision of multiple ESS (Benayas et al., 2009).

The full implementation of a network of GI will require considerable investment (Maes et al., 2015a). For example, Nauman et al. (2011) reported that the implementation of individual GI projects across different countries in the EU ranged from €0.5 to €5 million. The UE already have policy mechanisms into place to foster these kinds of management regimes towards multifunctional landscapes. The EU's Strategy of Green Infrastructure is supported by some actions under target 2 of the Biodiversity Strategy (EC, 2011), such as the restoration of degraded habitats or the No-Net-Loss, and there are some funding mechanisms available to help implement this network of GI. Some sources of co-funding by Member States include Structural and Cohesion funds, European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development, or the European Fund for Strategic

Investment. Given the contribution of agricultural and forestry areas to this network, some of these funding programs will play a key role in funding and ensuring the implementation of the network of GI. For example, the Common Agriculture Policy (CAP 2014-2020) includes the designation of Ecological Focus Areas in agricultural land. These are areas such as margins or buffer strips that contribute to provision of ESS like pollination, biological control or soil erosion prevention (Bommarco et al. 2013). However, further policy development will be necessary to ensure that these funding opportunities are accessible and adequately used to help implement and manage the network of GI, and avoid similar issues reported at the implementation of biodiversity conservation programmes (Hermoso et al., 2017). For example, funds available under these different funding schemes are not earmarked for conservation and then not secured for actions directly related with the implementation of Natura 2000 and conservation of biodiversity (Kettunen et al, 2009). A stronger integration of the Natura 2000 and the future network of GI in mainstream EU funding schemes is needed to ensure that the opportunities available in the EU's budget are completely released and funds used adequately (European Court of Auditors, 2017).

In return, the investment in GI delivers value to society through the ESS provided by the habitats under management (Vandermeulen et al. 2011, de Groot et al. 2012). Similar to the Natura 2000, with management cost estimated in €550 – €1150 million annually (Kettunen et al. 2011), contributes with ESS valued in €200--€300 billion a year at present (European Commission, 2013b).

The network of GI designed in this study is based on estimates of ESS provision potential or capacity (Syrbe, et al., 2017) following recommendations by EU (European Environmental Agency, 2014). Therefore, we have not accounted for demand for

services, favouring the selection of areas with the highest potential for ESS, regardless their proximity to the beneficiaries of the service (Vallecillo et al., 2018). These areas are, on the other hand, in better condition as we showed, with a greater potential for providing ESS and easier to manage. Moreover, the demand for most of the provisioning ESS considered in this study does not necessarily need to be fulfilled in areas close to the beneficiaries (e.g., Carbon retention). Whenever this was the case, that was accounted for in the estimates of the ESS potential. For example, Recreational opportunity was already weighted by accessibility by population in the estimates used, so areas with the highest potential for this ESS were also accessible to people that might demand the ESS. This planning exercise could potentially accommodate different estimates of ESS, including the ESS flows between the areas where they are supplied and where they are demanded to fit alternative objectives in designing future networks of GI. Defining these objectives and using adequate information to reflect them is critical. For example, the use of potential supply maps, like those used in this study, could direct management efforts towards areas with high ESS provision potential but no easy access or ESS demand and, therefore, with limited benefit for humans. On the other hand, the use potential-use supply of ESS could deliver solutions driven by accessibility of ESS by end users (Vallecillo et al., 2018; Cimon-Morin et al., 2014).

The multifunctional character of this network of GI is an opportunity to enhance co-benefits of landscape co-management for different objectives: biodiversity conservation and maintenance of ESS. However, it also poses important challenges, as not all ESS are equally compatible with conservation purposes or even compatible among them (Howe et al., 2014). For example, realising the potential of some ESS, especially provisioning services such as water or wood provisioning, could risk biodiversity or

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maintenance of other ESS (Maes et al., 2012; Schröter et al., 2014). Here, we only considered regulating services, like in previous exercises (Vallecillo et al., 2018), to avoid potential trade-offs within the network of GI. Further planning would be needed to incorporate these additional ESS and address potential trade-offs with other ESS and biodiversity conservation more explicitly. For example, Lanzas et al. (2019) and Domisch et al (2019) designed a network of GI for Catalonia and the Danube River basin respectively, including a “production zone” where access to these provisioning services could be granted while minimising potential impacts on PAs and the network of GI. Integrated planning exercises that address potential trade-offs between competing objectives are key to deliver management recommendations that embrace the multitude of interests that co-occur in space (e.g., Verhagen et al., 2018) and then to design future networks of GI.

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Table 2. Proportion of EU included under each management zone in the best solution for the 25% target on ESS and both planning scenarios.

Table 1. Marxan with Zones input files, as used in this study.

File	Purpose
Planning units	Lists all planning units included in the analyses, their costs and status
Species	Lists all conservation features included in the analyses (species, habitats and ecosystem services), targets and SPF
Puvspr	Contains the distribution of conservation features across planning units
Boundary	Lists pairwise connections among planning units that would apply penalties if not selected together
Zones	List of all management zones to be considered
Cost	Lists all potential costs applicable to planning units
Zone cost	Determines what costs to be applied to each management zone
Zone target	Lists targets for each conservation feature under each management zone
Zone boundary	Determines the spatial relationship between management zones
Pu lock	Lists those planning units to be locked in under a given management zone

Table 2. Proportion of EU included under each management zone in the best solution for the 25% target on ESS and both Marxan with Zones planning scenarios.

Target ESS	Scenario					
	No management	EU-based Conservation zone	Green infrastructure	No management	Country-based Conservation zone	Green infrastructure
5%	0.46	0.26	0.28	0.47	0.26	0.26
10%	0.46	0.26	0.28	0.47	0.26	0.27
25%	0.46	0.26	0.28	0.44	0.26	0.30
50%	0.23	0.26	0.50	0.19	0.26	0.55

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Figure 1. Average coverage of species and habitats distribution and ESS under the two management zones spatially prioritised in the study. Bars show average (\pm SE) proportion of the total distribution of species and habitats or total amount of ESS covered under each management zone for two alternative planning scenarios (EU-based vs. country-based) and two different targets on ESS (25% and 50%).

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Figure 4. Proportion of land cover coverage under each management zone prioritised in this study under two alternative planning scenarios (EU-based vs. country-based) for two different target levels (25% and 50%). Land cover classes from Corine Land Cover 2012 (EEA, 2016) were grouped into four types: urban/ industrial, agriculture, natural and wetlands (Supplementary Table 6).

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

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Appendix B. Proportion of target achieved for each ESS under the Country-based planning scenario in the Marxan with Zones analysis, reported by country, for the four different targets tested. In bold, ESS that did not achieve the target.

Appendix C. Spatial distribution of the two management zones prioritised in this study, under two alternative planning scenarios (EU-based vs. country-based) for four different targets on ESS.

Appendix D. Area (units = 10^6 km^2) of each management zone selected within each country for a 25% on ESS target under the two alternative planning scenarios. The proportional change between both scenarios ($\text{Area EU-based} - \text{Area country-based} / \text{Area EU-based}$) is also shown. Negative values show larger areas selected under the country-based scenario.

Appendix E. Area (units= 10^6 km^2) of each management zone selected within each country for a 50% on ESS target under the two alternative planning scenarios. The proportional change between both scenarios ($\text{Area EU-based} - \text{Area country-based} / \text{Area EU-based}$) is also shown. Negative values show larger areas selected under the country-based scenario.

Appendix F. Within country proportional difference in the Connectivity Index (CInx) between Natura 2000 and solutions [$\text{Difference} = (\text{CInx}_{\text{solution}} - \text{CInx}_{\text{Natura}}) / \text{CInx}_{\text{solution}}$].

Appendix G. Within country proportional difference in the CInx [$\text{Difference} = (\text{CInx}_{\text{EU}} - \text{CInx}_{\text{country}}) / \text{CI}_{\text{EU}}$] for solutions obtained in Marxan with zones. Raw values of CInx for each country can be found in Appendix F.

Appendix H. Coverage of four classes of land cover in the network of Green Infrastructure, for the EU-based planning scenario and a target on ESS of 25%. The distribution of the Conservation management zone is also shown.

Appendix A. Area (units= 10³ km²) of different types of land uses (EEA, 2016) across the network of GI prioritised in this study (conservation and GI zones) under the two alternative planning scenarios: EU-based vs. Country-based and change between them for two targets on ESS (25% and 50%). Results are also aggregated by main types of land uses (Urban/Industrial, Agriculture, Naturalised and Wetlands).

Code	Land use type	Target 25% ESS			Target 50% ESS		
		EU- GI	Country- GI	Change GI	EU- GI	Country- GI	Change GI
1	Continuous urban fabric	0.1	0.1	0	0.2	0.5	-0.3
2	Discontinuous urban fabric	10.5	19.6	-9.1	10.5	19.6	-9.1
3	Industrial or commercial units	0.3	0.4	-0.1	0.3	0.4	-0.1
5	Port areas	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	Airports	0.1	0.1	0	0.1	0.1	0
7	Mineral extraction sites	0.6	0.7	-0.1	0.6	0.7	-0.1
	Total Urban/ Industrial	11.7	21.3	-9.6	11.7	21.3	-9.6
12	Non-irrigated arable land	691.3	907.9	-216.6	691.3	907.9	-216.6
13	Permanently irrigated land	22.5	26.6	-4.1	22.5	26.6	-4.1
14	Rice fields	3.7	4	-0.3	3.7	4	-0.3
15	Vineyards	19	25.2	-6.2	19	25.2	-6.2
16	Fruit trees and berry plantations	13.3	15.5	-2.2	13.3	15.5	-2.2
17	Olive groves	25.2	33.7	-8.5	25.2	33.7	-8.5
18	Pastures	165.9	223.4	-57.5	165.9	223.4	-57.5
19	Annual crops associated with permanent crops	2.3	2.2	0.1	2.3	2.2	0.1
20	Complex cultivation patterns	57.7	75.6	-17.9	57.7	75.6	-17.9
21	Land principally occupied by agriculture, with significant areas of natural vegetation	22.8	25	-2.2	22.8	25	-2.2
22	Agro-forestry areas	21.2	22.8	-1.6	21.2	22.8	-1.6
	Total Agriculture	1044.9	1361.9	-317	1044.9	1361.9	-317
23	Broad-leaved forest	233.5	247.2	-13.7	233.5	247.2	-13.7
24	Coniferous forest	622.5	504.8	117.7	622.5	504.8	117.7

25	Mixed forest	111.5	101.6	9.9	111.5	101.6	9.9
26	Natural grasslands	38.1	38.1	0	38.1	38.1	0
27	Moors and heathland	38.6	39.3	-0.7	38.6	39.3	-0.7
28	Sclerophyllous vegetation	45.6	49.2	-3.6	45.6	49.2	-3.6
29	Transitional woodland-shrub	37.6	34.4	3.2	37.6	34.4	3.2
31	Bare rocks	6.4	6.1	0.3	6.4	6.1	0.3
32	Sparsely vegetated areas	9.7	8.7	1	9.7	8.7	1
33	Burnt areas	0	0	0	0	0	0
34	Glaciers and perpetual snow	0.4	0.3	0.1	0.4	0.3	0.1
	Total Natural	1143.9	1029.7	114.2	1143.9	1029.7	114.2
35	Inland marshes	0	0	0	0	0	0
36	Peat bogs	26.2	25.2	1	26.2	25.2	1
37	Salt marshes	0	0	0	0	0	0
38	Salines	0	0	0	0	0	0
39	Intertidal flats	0	0.1	-0.1	0	0.1	-0.1
40	Water courses	0	0.1	-0.1	0	0.1	-0.1
41	Water bodies	29.2	23.1	6.1	29.2	23.1	6.1
42	Coastal lagoons	0.3	0.3	0	0.3	0.3	0
43	Estuaries	0.5	0.5	0	0.5	0.5	0
44	Sea and ocean	92.9	112.7	-19.8	92.9	112.7	-19.8
	Total Wetlands	149.1	162	-12.9	149.1	162	-12.9
48		0.2	0.2	0	0.2	0.2	0
255	No Data	16.1	13.8	2.3	16.1	13.8	2.3
		16.3	14	2.3	16.3	14	2.3

Reference:

EEA (2016). Corine Land Cover 2012. Available at: <https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover/clc-2012>

Appendix B. Proportion of target achieved for each ESS under the Country-based planning scenario in the Marxan with Zones analysis, reported by country, for the four different targets tested. In bold, ESS that did not achieve the target.

Country	Ecosystem service	Planning scenario			
		ESS5	ESS10	ESS25	ESS50
Austria	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Austria	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Austria	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Austria	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Austria	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Belgium	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Belgium	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Belgium	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Belgium	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Belgium	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Bulgaria	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.52
Bulgaria	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.88
Bulgaria	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.67
Bulgaria	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.70
Bulgaria	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Croatia	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.87
Croatia	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Croatia	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.85
Croatia	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.78
Croatia	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Cyprus	Carbon retention	1.00	0.66	0.26	0.13
Cyprus	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Cyprus	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Cyprus	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Cyprus	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Czech Republic	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.80
Czech Republic	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Czech Republic	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Czech Republic	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Czech Republic	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Denmark	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Denmark	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Denmark	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Denmark	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Denmark	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Estonia	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Estonia	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Estonia	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Estonia	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Estonia	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

Finland	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Finland	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Finland	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Finland	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Finland	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
France	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
France	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
France	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
France	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
France	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Germany	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Germany	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Germany	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Germany	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Germany	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Greece	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.90
Greece	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Greece	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Greece	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Greece	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Hungary	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Hungary	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Hungary	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Hungary	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Hungary	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Ireland	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Ireland	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Ireland	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Ireland	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Ireland	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Italy	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Italy	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Italy	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Italy	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Italy	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Latvia	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Latvia	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Latvia	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Latvia	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Latvia	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Lithuania	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Lithuania	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Lithuania	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Lithuania	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Lithuania	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

Luxembourg	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.86
Luxembourg	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Luxembourg	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Luxembourg	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Luxembourg	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Netherlands	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Netherlands	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Netherlands	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Netherlands	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Netherlands	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Poland	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.90
Poland	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Poland	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Poland	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Poland	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Portugal	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Portugal	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Portugal	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Portugal	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Portugal	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Romania	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.90
Romania	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Romania	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Romania	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Romania	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Slovakia	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.72
Slovakia	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Slovakia	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.87
Slovakia	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.89
Slovakia	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Slovenia	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.83
Slovenia	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Slovenia	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.67
Slovenia	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.66
Slovenia	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Spain	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Spain	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Spain	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.85
Spain	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.89
Spain	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Sweden	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Sweden	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Sweden	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Sweden	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Sweden	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

Hermoso, V., Morán-Ordóñez, A., Lanzas, M., Brotons, Ll. (2019). Designing a network of Green Infrastructure for the EU. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 196, 103732.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2019.103732>

United Kingdom	Carbon retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
United Kingdom	Pollination	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
United Kingdom	Recreational opportunities	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
United Kingdom	Soil retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
United Kingdom	Water retention	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

Appendix C. Spatial distribution of the two management zones prioritised in this study, under two alternative planning scenarios (EU-based vs. country-based) for four different targets on ESS.

Appendix D. Area (units= 10⁶ km²) of each management zone selected within each country for a 25% on ESS target under the two alternative planning scenarios. The proportional change between both scenarios (Area EU-based – Area country-based/ Area EU-based) is also shown. Negative values show larger areas selected under the country-based scenario.

Country	EU-based			Country-based			Change (EU-Country)		
	No managt.	Conserv.	Green infrast.	No managt.	Conserv.	Green infrast.	No managt.	Conserv.	Green infrast.
Spain	127.4	212.2	186.2	129.6	212.2	184	-0.02	0.00	0.01
Greece	41.9	62.2	63.7	47.5	62.5	57.8	-0.13	0.00	0.09
Portugal	39.1	31.5	30.4	39.8	31.5	29.7	-0.02	0.00	0.02
Italy	134.2	89	105.9	140.2	89.2	99.7	-0.04	0.00	0.06
Cyprus	6.7	2.8	3.1	6.2	2.8	3.6	0.07	0.00	-0.16
United Kingdom	169.1	61.5	60.5	158.4	61.6	71.1	0.06	0.00	-0.18
France	315.9	113.8	141.2	308.7	114	148.2	0.02	0.00	-0.05
Bulgaria	15.2	56.6	44.9	13.9	56.7	46.1	0.09	0.00	-0.03
Croatia	7.2	33.2	29.6	8.4	33.3	28.3	-0.17	0.00	0.04
Romania	105.6	73.9	67.4	105.1	73.8	68	0.00	0.00	-0.01
Slovenia	0.4	11.6	9.2	0.8	11.6	8.8	-1.00	0.00	0.04
Hungary	27.3	29.1	38.4	32.1	29.1	33.6	-0.18	0.00	0.13
Austria	35.5	19.5	29.7	39	19.7	26	-0.10	-0.01	0.12
Germany	178.4	84.3	105.3	172.9	84.2	110.9	0.03	0.00	-0.05
Slovakia	6	19.9	23.4	11.4	19.9	18	-0.90	0.00	0.23
Czech Republic	49.6	14.2	15.2	43.1	14.2	21.7	0.13	0.00	-0.43
Belgium	20.4	5.5	5.3	17.5	5.5	8.2	0.14	0.00	-0.55
Luxembourg	0.1	1.1	1.2	0.1	1.1	1.2	0.00	0.00	0.00
Poland	143.2	86.8	90.3	138.2	86.7	95.4	0.03	0.00	-0.06
Netherlands	20	12.4	8.7	17.1	12.4	11.6	0.15	0.00	-0.33
Ireland	40.3	20.8	20.7	37	20.8	24	0.08	0.00	-0.16
Denmark	27.3	14.6	15.7	27.6	14.6	15.4	-0.01	0.00	0.02
Lithuania	39.5	11.5	19.3	37.9	11.6	20.8	0.04	-0.01	-0.08
Sweden	328.3	70.3	77.5	284.5	70.4	121.2	0.13	0.00	-0.56
Latvia	36.9	12.5	20.1	36.4	12.4	20.7	0.01	0.01	-0.03
Estonia	14.6	16.8	22	15.5	16.9	21	-0.06	-0.01	0.05
Finland	213.3	59.6	86.7	186.9	59.6	113.1	0.12	0.00	-0.30
Total	2143.4	1227.2	1321.6	2055.8	1228.3	1408.1			

Appendix E. Area (units= 10⁶ km²) of each management zone selected within each country for a 50% on ESS target under the two alternative planning scenarios. The proportional change between both scenarios (Area EU-based – Area country-based/ Area EU-based) is also shown. Negative values show larger areas selected under the country-based scenario.

Country	EU-based			Country-based			Change (EU-Country)		
	No managt.	Conserv.	Green infrast.	No managt.	Conserv.	Green infrast.	No managt.	Conserv.	Green infrast.
Spain	50.7	212	263.1	0.9	211.9	313	0.98	0.00	-0.19
Greece	19.3	62.1	86.4	1.3	62.1	104.4	0.93	0.00	-0.21
Portugal	12	31.5	57.5	15.6	31	54.4	-0.30	0.02	0.05
Italy	84.1	89	156	49.2	89.1	190.8	0.41	0.00	-0.22
Cyprus	6	2.8	3.8	1.9	2.8	7.9	0.68	0.00	-1.08
United Kingdom	135.3	61.4	94.4	86.5	61.4	143.2	0.36	0.00	-0.52
France	221.6	113.8	235.5	164.8	113.7	292.4	0.26	0.00	-0.24
Bulgaria	4.9	56.6	55.2	0	56.6	60.1	1.00	0.00	-0.09
Croatia	3.8	33.1	33.1	0	33.2	36.8	1.00	0.00	-0.11
Romania	62.3	73.7	110.9	7.5	73.7	165.7	0.88	0.00	-0.49
Slovenia	0	11.6	9.6	0	11.6	9.6		0.00	0.00
Hungary	13.3	29.1	52.4	1.4	29.1	64.3	0.89	0.00	-0.23
Austria	9.7	19.5	55.5	19.1	19.7	45.9	-0.97	-0.01	0.17
Germany	84.9	84.3	198.8	97.3	84.2	186.5	-0.15	0.00	0.06
Slovakia	2.7	19.9	26.7	0	19.9	29.4	1.00	0.00	-0.10
Czech Republic	37.6	14.2	27.2	19.1	14.2	45.7	0.49	0.00	-0.68
Belgium	17.4	5.5	8.3	9.8	5.5	15.9	0.44	0.00	-0.92
Luxembourg	0	1.1	1.3	0	1.1	1.3		0.00	0.00
Poland	94.6	86.7	139	40.5	86.8	193	0.57	0.00	-0.39
Netherlands	14.5	12.4	14.2	8.3	12.4	20.4	0.43	0.00	-0.44
Ireland	29.2	20.8	31.8	16.3	20.8	44.7	0.44	0.00	-0.41
Denmark	22.3	14.6	20.7	14.1	14.6	28.9	0.37	0.00	-0.40
Lithuania	14.8	11.5	44	23.1	11.6	35.6	-0.56	-0.01	0.19
Sweden	88.1	70.2	317.8	164.2	70.1	241.8	-0.86	0.00	0.24
Latvia	11.1	12.5	45.9	17.5	12.4	39.6	-0.58	0.01	0.14
Estonia	3.5	16.9	33	7.9	16.9	28.6	-1.26	0.00	0.13
Finland	56.3	59.5	243.8	111.1	59.5	189	-0.97	0.00	0.22
Total	1100	1226.3	2365.9	877.4	1225.9	2588.9			

Appendix F. Within country Connectivity Index (Clnx) values and proportional difference in the Clnx between Natura 2000 and solutions [Difference=(Clnx_{solution}-Clnx_{Natura2000})/Clnx_{solution}]. N2K stands for Natura 2000.

Country	ESS5				ESS10				ESS25				ESS50				
	N2K	Country	EU	Diff (N2K-Country)	Diff (N2K-EU)	Country	EU	Diff (N2K-Country)	Diff (N2K-EU)	Country	EU	Diff (N2K-Country)	Diff (N2K-EU)	Country	EU	Diff (N2K-Country)	Diff (N2K-EU)
Austria	0.40	0.78	0.79	0.48	0.49	0.78	0.83	0.48	0.51	0.81	0.81	0.50	0.50	0.90	0.95	0.55	0.57
Belgium	0.36	0.70	0.71	0.48	0.49	0.66	0.67	0.45	0.46	0.78	0.71	0.53	0.49	0.87	0.77	0.58	0.53
Bulgaria	0.59	0.91	0.90	0.36	0.35	0.83	0.83	0.29	0.30	0.92	0.92	0.37	0.36	1.00	0.97	0.41	0.40
Croatia	0.53	0.94	0.95	0.44	0.44	0.83	0.83	0.37	0.37	0.94	0.95	0.44	0.45	1.00	0.97	0.47	0.46
Cyprus	0.48	0.77	0.82	0.38	0.42	0.76	0.82	0.37	0.42	0.84	0.81	0.43	0.41	0.93	0.85	0.49	0.44
Czech Republic	0.40	0.73	0.72	0.45	0.45	0.69	0.68	0.42	0.42	0.78	0.72	0.49	0.45	0.88	0.80	0.55	0.50
Denmark	0.35	0.71	0.73	0.51	0.52	0.80	0.80	0.56	0.56	0.72	0.73	0.52	0.52	0.88	0.77	0.60	0.55
Estonia	0.41	0.83	0.83	0.50	0.51	0.84	0.83	0.51	0.50	0.83	0.83	0.50	0.51	0.92	0.96	0.55	0.57
Finland	0.49	0.83	0.83	0.41	0.41	0.78	0.79	0.38	0.38	0.82	0.83	0.40	0.41	0.88	0.95	0.44	0.49
France	0.40	0.78	0.79	0.48	0.49	0.71	0.73	0.43	0.45	0.80	0.79	0.49	0.49	0.90	0.86	0.55	0.53
Germany	0.37	0.79	0.79	0.52	0.53	0.80	0.80	0.53	0.53	0.81	0.79	0.54	0.53	0.90	0.91	0.58	0.59
Greece	0.47	0.85	0.85	0.45	0.45	0.70	0.71	0.33	0.34	0.85	0.86	0.45	0.46	0.99	0.95	0.53	0.51
Hungary	0.39	0.78	0.82	0.50	0.53	0.85	0.86	0.54	0.55	0.80	0.82	0.51	0.53	0.99	0.91	0.61	0.57
Ireland	0.44	0.80	0.80	0.46	0.46	0.77	0.78	0.44	0.44	0.82	0.80	0.47	0.46	0.93	0.84	0.53	0.48
Italy	0.40	0.79	0.80	0.49	0.49	0.94	0.94	0.57	0.57	0.79	0.80	0.49	0.49	0.93	0.88	0.56	0.54
Latvia	0.34	0.69	0.67	0.51	0.50	0.88	0.88	0.61	0.61	0.74	0.70	0.54	0.52	0.90	0.93	0.62	0.63
Lithuania	0.30	0.66	0.67	0.55	0.56	0.89	0.93	0.67	0.68	0.72	0.68	0.58	0.56	0.85	0.89	0.65	0.67
Luxembourg	0.33	0.96	0.96	0.65	0.65	0.96	0.96	0.65	0.65	0.96	0.96	0.65	0.65	1.00	1.00	0.67	0.67
Netherlands	0.49	0.78	0.79	0.38	0.38	0.80	0.80	0.39	0.39	0.82	0.79	0.41	0.38	0.92	0.85	0.47	0.43
Poland	0.46	0.80	0.80	0.43	0.43	0.79	0.79	0.42	0.43	0.81	0.80	0.44	0.43	0.94	0.88	0.52	0.48
Portugal	0.47	0.78	0.77	0.40	0.39	0.91	0.92	0.49	0.49	0.78	0.78	0.40	0.40	0.92	0.95	0.49	0.50
Romania	0.49	0.80	0.80	0.39	0.39	0.78	0.78	0.37	0.38	0.80	0.80	0.39	0.39	0.98	0.89	0.50	0.45
Slovakia	0.47	0.89	0.92	0.47	0.49	0.79	0.80	0.40	0.41	0.89	0.93	0.47	0.49	1.00	0.96	0.53	0.51
Slovenia	0.59	0.97	0.98	0.40	0.40	0.79	0.79	0.26	0.26	0.97	0.98	0.40	0.40	1.00	1.00	0.41	0.41
Spain	0.52	0.88	0.88	0.41	0.41	0.78	0.80	0.34	0.36	0.88	0.88	0.41	0.42	1.00	0.95	0.48	0.46
Sweden	0.52	0.83	0.83	0.38	0.37	0.97	0.98	0.47	0.47	0.84	0.83	0.39	0.38	0.91	0.94	0.43	0.45
United Kingdom	0.40	0.78	0.78	0.48	0.48	0.73	0.72	0.44	0.44	0.81	0.78	0.50	0.48	0.91	0.84	0.55	0.52
Average	0.44	0.81	0.81	0.46	0.46	0.81	0.82	0.45	0.46	0.83	0.82	0.47	0.46	0.93	0.90	0.53	0.52

Appendix G. Within country proportional difference in the Clnx [Difference=(Clnx_{EU}-Clnx_{country})/Clnx_{EU}] for solutions obtained in Marxan with zones. Raw values of Clnx for each country can be found in Appendix F.

Country	Target ESS			
	5%	10%	25%	50%
Austria	0.12	0.12	0.05	0.14
Belgium	0.07	0.04	-0.41	-0.76
Bulgaria	-0.02	0.02	-0.02	-0.06
Croatia	0.02	-0.04	0.02	-0.06
Cyprus	0.10	0.10	-0.12	-0.66
Czech Republic	-0.01	0.04	-0.29	-0.57
Denmark	0.05	0.02	>0.01	-0.36
Estonia	0.02	-0.09	0.02	0.11
Finland	-0.02	0.02	-0.18	0.22
France	0.03	0.05	-0.04	-0.2
Germany	0.02	0.03	-0.04	0.05
Greece	0.02	0.06	0.04	-0.14
Hungary	0.11	0.04	0.07	-0.20
Ireland	0.02	0.01	-0.11	-0.33
Italy	0.02	0.01	0.03	-0.18
Latvia	0.01	>0.01	-0.06	0.13
Lithuania	0.04	0.14	-0.10	0.16
Luxembourg	>0.01	>0.01	>0.01	>0.01
Netherlands	0.05	>0.01	-0.19	-0.3
Poland	0.01	0.03	-0.04	-0.3
Portugal	0.01	0.02	>0.01	0.06
Romania	0.01	0.01	-0.01	-0.38
Slovakia	0.11	0.02	0.13	-0.08
Slovenia	0.03	0.02	0.03	>0.01
Spain	>0.01	0.16	>0.01	-0.13
Sweden	0.02	0.03	-0.32	0.21
United Kingdom	0.01	-0.02	-0.11	-0.38
Average	0.04	0.04	0.09	0.23

Appendix H. Spatial distribution of planning units added to the already locked in Natura 2000 under two alternative planning scenarios (EU-based vs. country-based, 25% target on ESS) obtained when following the single-zoning planning approach (standard Marxan analysis). Planning units locked in solutions are shown in orange and new planning units added to fulfil the ESS and biodiversity targets are in blue.

Appendix I. Within country Connectivity Index (CI_{nx}) values for the Natura 2000 (N2K), and single-zone planning solutions (standard Marxan) under two alternative planning scenarios: UE-based and Country-based. Solutions for targets 5% and 10% were not different to 25% and, therefore, not showed here.

Country	ESS25		ESS50		
	N2K	EU	Country	EU	Country
Austria	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.38	0.50
Belgium	0.36	0.36	0.38	0.35	0.47
Bulgaria	0.59	0.58	0.58	0.60	0.58
Croatia	0.53	0.52	0.52	0.59	0.53
Cyprus	0.48	0.48	0.52	0.53	0.56
Czech Republic	0.40	0.40	0.37	0.37	0.46
Denmark	0.35	0.34	0.35	0.38	0.47
Estonia	0.41	0.41	0.41	0.67	0.51
Finland	0.49	0.49	0.42	0.58	0.52
France	0.40	0.40	0.37	0.43	0.47
Germany	0.37	0.37	0.38	0.41	0.49
Greece	0.47	0.45	0.45	0.49	0.50
Hungary	0.39	0.39	0.39	0.44	0.47
Ireland	0.44	0.44	0.43	0.53	0.48
Italy	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.46	0.51
Latvia	0.34	0.34	0.37	0.44	0.52
Lithuania	0.30	0.30	0.32	0.40	0.47
Luxembourg	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.56	0.42
Netherlands	0.49	0.49	0.48	0.49	0.51
Poland	0.46	0.45	0.45	0.48	0.48
Portugal	0.47	0.46	0.46	0.46	0.50
Romania	0.49	0.49	0.49	0.48	0.50
Slovakia	0.47	0.46	0.46	0.52	0.49
Slovenia	0.59	0.59	0.59	0.63	0.64
Spain	0.52	0.51	0.51	0.53	0.54
Sweden	0.52	0.52	0.42	0.48	0.50
United Kingdom	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.46	0.51
Average	0.44	0.44	0.43	0.49	0.50

Appendix H. Coverage of four classes of land cover in the network of Green Infrastructure, for the EU-based planning scenario and a target on ESS of 25%. The distribution of the Conservation management zone is also shown (orange).

